

Resettlement Problems of Gosikhurd Irrigation Project Affected Persons in Maharashtra State

Dr. Sherumal Pandhari Shende

Shri. Shahu Mandir Mahavidyalaya, Pune

Corresponding Author - Dr. Sherumal Pandhari Shende

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Abstract:

Gosikhurd Irrigation Project is a major Irrigation Project of Maharashtra state. 93 villages are fully affected and another 107 villages are partially affected due to this Project. The study is carried out in 07 Affected Villages of Bhandara district which are being shifted in 07 Rehabilitated Villages. In this study comparison of project affected persons before and after economic condition in construction of Gosikhurd irrigation dam. The project was declared as 'National Irrigation Project' by the government of India. The project is still incomplete and there are gross irregularities in rehabilitation of effected people. This research is largely base on the primary data collected through questionnaire and secondary data collected from government documents, reports etc and on the information collected from officials, environmentalists, activists and other concerned people.

Keywords: *Gosikhurd Irrigation Project, Project affected people, Rehabilitation and Resettlement, Affected village, Rehabilitated village, Vidirbha Irrigation Development Corporation.*

Introduction:

Development projects have often displaced a large number of people in different parts of the world. The displaced are mainly the poor and the dispossessed, who do not have political and economic power to turn policies in their favor. This perhaps explains the casual attitude of governments throughout the world. Lack of accurate arrangements to safeguard the interest of the Project Affected Persons is a universal phenomena. Large dams have been a major cause of human displacement. What is important here is how to deal with the people who are adversely affected by major irrigation dams, namely PAPs. Resettlement of the PAPs is a major challenge to the government. Any infrastructural development project such as irrigation dams are the symbol of national progress, though they bring economic prosperity

but at the same time they create an unpleasant and undesirable displacement of section of population from their ancestral habitat, uprooting them from their immovable properties, their live stock wealth, religious and educational institutions etc. This makes rehabilitation the most sensitive yet important aspect.

Study Objectives:

1. To analyze the trend of Rehabilitation and Resettlement of GIP.
2. To understand the compensation to of project affected under rehabilitation scheme of GIP.
3. Do displaced people currently have opportunities to recreate sustainable livelihoods?
4. Have the project-affected people been able to adapt to resettlement in the different areas and utilize

the compensation packages offered to them?

5. Did R&R policies for project-affected people provide them with the tools to create and sustain new employment?

Research Methodology:

The study is carried out only 07 fully affected villages of Bhandara district on the base of primary and secondary data. Primary data collected through questioners and The secondary data was collected from government documents, reports, various journals, magazines, news papers. This research is a descriptive study in nature. the stud

Real Cost of the Project:

The inter-district Gosikhurd irrigation project here which was launched 25 years ago, has become a saga of neglect and disappointment for people in Vidarbha region, since its still lying unfinished. The ambitious project was expected to irrigate about 2,50,800 hectares of land in three districts in eastern Vidarbha (Nagpur, Bhandara and Chandrapur) but so far it has created an irrigation potential for only 36,894 hectares. Over the decades, the government has spent about Rs 6,073 crores and would require an estimate of another Rs 7,665 crores to finish the project, which was inaugurated by late Prime Minister Rajiv Gandhi on April 22, 1988. According to sources, the cost of the project has now escalated to a whopping Rs 13,600 crore - roughly 40 times the original estimate. But real benefits are yet to be passed on to the people of Bhandara, Nagpur and Chandrapur districts who will be immensely benefited once this mega project starts irrigating land, providing

drinking water and supplying water to Ordnance factory Bhandara.

Resettlement of Project Affected Persons:

Development projects have often displaced a large number of people in different parts of the world. The displaced are mainly the poor and the dispossessed, who do not have political and economic power to turn policies *in* their favor. This perhaps explains the casual attitude of governments throughout the world. Lack of accurate arrangements to safeguard the interest of the Project Affected Persons (PAPs) is a universal phenomena. Large dams have been a major cause of human displacement. It is argued that Such projects being bring benefits to a much larger number of people in terms of electricity power generation, irrigation of huge areas of land etc. However, this has been a subject of continuous debate in various circles. What is important here is how to deal with the people who are adversely affected by major dams, namely PAPs. Resettlement of the PAPs is a major challenge to the governments.

Cash Compensation:

Internationally land-for-land is the preferred resettlement strategy. However, where this is not possible adequate cash compensation needs to be provided. Most international organizations' policies require the rate of compensation for acquired land and structures to be calculated at full replacement cost. The full replacement cost takes into account the fair market value of the land and structures, transaction costs such as registration fees and transfer taxes, and relocation and restoration costs. In certain countries where no land market

exists, such as China, land compensation is calculated based on the annual output value of the land. This value takes into account factors such as the type and quality of land and the amount invested in the land in the form of improvements. In certain the cases, concerns have been raised regarding deductions made to compensation payments. For instance, in the case of Cambodia's Highway One improvement project, deductions were made for depreciation in the value of building and structures, the value of salvageable material, and nonstructural assets such as fruit trees. In cases of economic displacement, the level of compensation should take into account loss of earnings and earning potential.

Losses of Economic Development:

Often suitable replacement land for project-affected persons who are dependent on agriculture is unavailable. In such cases, vocational training and other forms of capacity building, such as providing credit facilities to start a business, would enable them to find an alternative livelihood and facilitate the transition to non-agricultural activities. Asian Development Bank and the World Bank, seek to enable project-affected persons to share in project benefits to improve their former living standards and income earning capacity. Frequently, a development project will create livelihood opportunities.

Losses of Actual Price of Land:

The value of land will differ based on whether it is irrigated agricultural land, non-irrigated agricultural land, pasture, forest, housing or commercial land. There are other qualitative differences in land, such as access to

water sources and sunk investments like water pumps. Often low-income households have a diversified livelihood strategy and combine agriculture with wage labour and small-scale enterprise. Accurately accounting for the value of land and all lost income streams could be a challenge.

Market Price & Land Compensation:

The amount of compensation against the market price of land has its limitations. In many regions, land transactions may not be properly documented and the full transaction value may be concealed to escape stamp duty. The market price will not take into account the appreciation of real estate prices as a result of the relevant development project. It may also exclude any intangible value owing to any social or cultural significance of the property.

Conclusion:

Project-affected persons have a right to adequate replacement land and structures a percentage of revenues from hydropower projects are required to be transferred for the development of the areas to which the displaced populations are relocated. The Gosikhurd Irrigation Project is Failure to provide adequate compensation would be a violation of their human rights and could lead to their indebtedness of project affected persons. Access to civic infrastructure and essential services such as health and education is not providing properly.

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